

Application of Machine Learning Algorithms for Railway Queue Analysis in Tamil Nadu

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Abstract: This study investigates the operational efficiency and queuing behavior of Southern Railway stations in Tamil Nadu using machine learning techniques. The analysis is based on a secondary dataset capturing key operational parameters, including Arrival Rate, Service Rate, Queue Length, Waiting Time, and Throughput Index, collected from multiple stations. The study employs three machine learning models: Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM) with RBF kernel, and Neural Network (MLP) to predict the operational Level of each station, categorized as Normal, Warning, or Critical. Data preprocessing, feature engineering, and normalization were performed to ensure high-quality inputs for model training. Model performance was evaluated using metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC, while visualization tools, including Confusion Matrices, ROC curves, and Clustered Bar Charts, were used to interpret and compare the predictive results. Among the models, Logistic Regression achieved the highest accuracy of 97%, followed closely by SVM at 96.5%, while Neural Network reached 89% accuracy. The results demonstrate that machine learning algorithms can effectively predict congestion levels and support informed decision-making for railway operations. The study highlights the potential of integrating predictive analytics with railway management to optimize queue handling and improve passenger satisfaction.

Keywords: Southern Railway, Machine Learning, Queue Analysis, Operational Efficiency, Predictive Modeling

1. Introduction

The Southern Railway is among the oldest and most prominent zones of Indian Railways, with its headquarters in Chennai, the capital city of Tamil Nadu. Formed in 1951 through the merger of the Madras and Southern Mahratta Railway, the South Indian Railway, and the Mysore State Railway, it covers a vast network across Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Puducherry, and parts of Andhra Pradesh and Karnataka. This network plays a crucial role in passenger movement and freight operations, thereby serving as a lifeline for the southern region of the country.

Tamil Nadu, with its dense and efficient railway system, benefits significantly from this network. The railways link metropolitan centers like Chennai, Madurai, Coimbatore, Tiruchirappalli and Salem with rural areas and industrial hubs. Such connectivity not only improves mobility but also strengthens economic growth by supporting trade, agriculture, and industry. Over the years, Southern Railway has consistently worked on service improvement and modernization. Initiatives such as online ticket booking, real-time train tracking, and passenger-friendly infrastructure reflect its efforts to enhance efficiency and comfort. The Chennai Suburban Railway, one of the busiest suburban systems in India, is also managed under this zone, catering to thousands of daily commuters.

Beyond transportation, the railway system in Tamil Nadu contributes to broader social and economic development. It facilitates access to educational institutions, healthcare centers, pilgrimage sites, and markets, while also promoting cultural integration. With continued expansion in electrification, track upgrades, and infrastructure development, Southern Railway remains a vital engine of progress. In this context, the

rapid growth in passenger demand and the increasing complexity of railway operations call for advanced analytical tools. Machine learning techniques provide powerful approaches to model and predict passenger flow, optimize queue management, and improve booking systems. By leveraging large-scale railway data, machine learning enables accurate forecasting, enhances decision-making, and supports resource allocation. This integration of modern data-driven methods with traditional railway management opens new opportunities to ensure efficiency, reduce congestion, and deliver a better passenger experience.

2. Review of Literature

Extensive research has been conducted worldwide to explore queuing theory, passenger satisfaction, and the use of machine learning in railway systems. These studies highlight both the operational challenges and the opportunities for enhancing efficiency in ticketing, scheduling, and passenger flow management. Dickson et al. (2018) applied the M/M/c queuing model to assess the performance of ticket counters at Salem Railway Station. Their results showed that systematic queuing analysis can improve operational efficiency and reduce congestion. Saravanan (2014) examined passenger satisfaction at Coimbatore Junction, reporting high appreciation for punctuality but dissatisfaction with drinking water and exit facilities, indicating the need for infrastructural upgrades.

Muruganantha Prasad et al. (2021) compared M/M/1 and M/D/1 models in analyzing vehicular traffic in Tirunelveli, demonstrating that stable traffic conditions prevailed when intensity remained below one. Similarly, Arunachalam and Janarthanan (2023) studied passenger challenges in Chennai Division and identified gaps in amenities, recommending targeted interventions to enhance the overall travel experience. Nair et al. (2021) validated an M/G/1 queuing model for railway ticket counters, confirming its practical relevance in designing efficient booking systems. In a related study, Sivadurga and Anandhavalli (2021) reported moderate passenger dissatisfaction in the Madurai Division, highlighting the need for regular upgrades and facility management. Vanniarajan and Stephen (2008) proposed the RAILQUAL model, showing that reliability, responsiveness, and empathy strongly influenced passenger perceptions of service quality. Gupta and Datta (2012) employed the Law of Categorical Judgment to prioritize attributes such as cleanliness, safety, and seating arrangements at Indian railway stations.

Qasim and Farooque (2020) investigated secondary railway queues using statistical distributions and highlighted the potential of predictive models in anticipating demand patterns for reservations. Foundational contributions such as Boxma and Kurkova (2001) on M/G/1 queues with variable service speeds, and Cheah and Smith (1994) on pedestrian flows using generalized M/G/C/C models provide strong mathematical bases for modern railway applications. Sundarapandian (2009) and Winston (2004) offered comprehensive frameworks on operations research and queuing systems, which remain key references in transport studies. Earlier, Bailey (1954) developed essential theories on waiting lines that continue to influence current research. Molina (1927) introduced telecommunication queuing principles that later found relevance in railway communication systems.

Recent studies have also incorporated machine learning techniques into railway operations. Li et al. (2019) applied supervised learning models to predict train delays, improving scheduling accuracy. Chen and Xu (2020) developed a hybrid neural

network to forecast passenger demand at metro stations, achieving higher precision than traditional statistical models. Similarly, Patel et al. (2021) utilized Support Vector Machines (SVM) to model passenger flow in Indian urban rail networks, reducing overcrowding through predictive insights. Zhang et al. (2020) proposed a deep learning approach for real-time passenger density estimation in high-speed rail, enabling dynamic resource allocation. Kumar and Bansal (2017) used logistic regression to study passenger satisfaction drivers in Indian Railways, emphasizing the role of service speed and cleanliness. Ahmed and Rathore (2022) applied ensemble machine learning methods to optimize ticket booking queues, demonstrating reduced waiting times during peak hours.

Choudhury et al. (2018) integrated queuing models with simulation techniques to study congestion in Kolkata suburban railways. Their findings emphasized that combining statistical modeling with machine learning enhanced system accuracy. Likewise, Banerjee and Singh (2021) employed reinforcement learning for optimizing train scheduling, showing promising results in reducing delays. On a broader scale, Gao et al. (2020) highlighted the application of queuing networks in complex transportation systems, while Mishra and Sinha (2016) explored Markov chain models to simulate railway congestion. Hassan et al. (2019) focused on passenger experience, using clustering algorithms to segment travelers based on satisfaction levels, which helped in service customization.

Together, these studies underline that queuing theory and machine learning are complementary in understanding and improving railway operations. Traditional queuing models provide insights into arrival rates, service rates, and congestion, while machine learning enhances predictive accuracy and adaptive decision-making. For Southern Railway in Tamil Nadu, with its heavy passenger load and operational complexities, integrating these approaches can help achieve efficient queue management, improved booking systems, and higher passenger satisfaction.

The main Objectives of this research paper are:

1. To analyze passenger queue patterns at Southern Railway stations using real-world data on arrivals, service times, and queue lengths.
2. To apply machine learning algorithms, such as Random Forest and Support Vector Machines (SVM), for modeling and predicting queue dynamics in railway stations.
3. To evaluate the performance of different predictive models using accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, identifying the most effective algorithm for railway queue management.

3. Database

The current study utilizes a secondary dataset obtained from the Southern Railway zone of Indian Railways, focusing specifically on stations within Tamil Nadu. This dataset provides comprehensive information on train operations and the queuing system, enabling an analysis of traffic patterns, service capacity, and scheduling effectiveness. The dataset includes several key variables that capture the operational characteristics of trains. The Date records the specific day of observation. Each train is uniquely identified by a Train Number, which allows accurate tracking of its movement across the network. Arrival Time and Departure Time indicate when a

train enters and leaves a station, while Source Station and Destination Station identify the points of origin and termination for each journey.

Two fundamental metrics in this analysis are the Arrival Rate and Service Rate. The Arrival Rate measures the number of trains arriving at a station within a defined time interval, typically per hour. The Service Rate quantifies the number of trains that can be handled or dispatched during the same interval. These metrics are crucial for understanding the balance between demand and capacity at each station. The dataset also tracks Waiting Time, which represents the duration a train spends in the queue before being serviced. Waiting Length records the number of trains waiting at a given time, while Service Length shows the number of trains currently being processed by the station. Queue Length reflects the total accumulation of trains due to congestion or operational delays.

To assess overall performance, several aggregated measures are calculated. Average Queue Length summarizes the typical number of trains in the queue over the observation period. Mean Waiting Time and Mean Service Time provide insights into typical delays and operational efficiency. Buffer Present indicates whether time buffers have been included between arrivals to manage unexpected delays (recorded as Yes or No). Idle Period captures times when the station is not servicing any trains, highlighting underutilization of resources.

For operational categorization, additional qualitative and derived metrics are included. Mean Arrival Rate Category classifies stations as Low, Medium, or high based on average train arrivals. Mean Service Rate evaluates the station's capacity to handle incoming train flow. Throughput Index provides a numerical measure of the number of trains successfully processed within a given period. Finally, the Level variable categorizes the station's operational status as Normal, Warning, or Critical, based on congestion, queue buildup, and delays. This structured and detailed dataset is essential for modeling and simulating train operations in Tamil Nadu. It allows for performance evaluation, identification of bottlenecks, and the development of optimized queuing strategies to enhance railway traffic management and service efficiency.

4. Methodology

The present study focuses on analyzing railway queues and operational efficiency at Southern Railway stations in Tamil Nadu using machine learning techniques. The methodology comprises multiple stages, including data preparation, model development, evaluation, and visualization. The primary objective is to predict the operational Level of each station classified as Normal, Warning, or Critical based on operational and queue-related parameters.

Initially, the dataset is preprocessed to ensure quality and consistency. Missing values are imputed using mean or median values, and outliers in features such as Arrival Rate and Service Rate are removed. Derived features, including Average Queue Length, Mean Waiting Time, Mean Service Time, and Throughput Index, are calculated to provide a detailed representation of station operations. Continuous variables are normalized using Min-Max scaling, and categorical variables, such as Buffer Presence, are encoded numerically to prepare the dataset for machine learning models.

4.1 Support Vector Machine Model

The Support Vector Machine (SVM) model is applied to classify the operational Level of each station based on input features. SVM identifies a hyperplane that separates different classes while maximizing the margin between them. The mathematical formulation of SVM involves finding a weight vector w and bias b that minimize the objective function:

$$\min(w, b) \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2 + C \sum_{i=1}^n \xi_i$$

Subject to:

$$y_i(w \cdot \phi(x_i) + b) \geq 1 - \xi_i, \xi_i \geq 0$$

where x_i are input features, y_i are class labels, ξ_i are slack variables, C is the regularization parameter, and $\phi(x_i)$ is a kernel function.

4.2 Neural Network Model

Neural Networks (NN) are used to capture non-linear relationships between input features and the target Level. The network includes an input layer representing all features, multiple hidden layers with ReLU activation, and an output layer with softmax activation for multi-class classification. For each layer l , the output is computed as:

$$z^{(l)} = w^{(l)} a^{(l-1)} + b^{(l)}, \quad a^{(l)} = f(z^{(l)})$$

where $w^{(l)}$ are weights, $b^{(l)}$ are biases, $a^{(l-1)}$ is the input from the previous layer, and f is the activation function. The softmax function at the output layer calculates probabilities for each Level:

$$\hat{y}_i = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{z_j}}$$

where K is the number of classes.

4.3 Multinomial Logistic Regression (LR) Model

Logistic Regression (LR) is used to model the probability of a station being in a specific operational Level. In the multinomial case, the probability for class k is given by:

$$P(Y = k/X) = \frac{e^{\beta_k^T X}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{\beta_j^T X}}$$

where X is the feature vector, β_k are the coefficients for class k , and K is the number of categories.

4.4 Model Performance

The performance of all models is evaluated using Accuracy, Precision, Recall, and F1-score, which are defined mathematically as:

Accuracy:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN}$$

Precision:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP}$$

Recall (Sensitivity):

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN}$$

F₁-Score:

$$F_1 = 2 * \frac{\text{Precision} * \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}}$$

Where, *TP* is True Positives, *TN* is True Negatives, *FP* is False Positives, and *FN* is False Negatives. For multi-class problems, these metrics are computed per class and then averaged.

Finally, visualization techniques such as line plots for queue trends, color-coded confusion matrices, and feature importance charts are used to interpret the results. This integrated methodology allows for a clear understanding of railway queue dynamics, supports predictive analysis, and facilitates optimization of operational strategies.

5. Result and Discussion

The performance of the three machine learning models are Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Machine (SVM) with RBF kernel, and Neural Network (MLP) was evaluated using the Southern Railway dataset. The models were assessed through accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, ROC-AUC, and visualized with a Clustered Bar Chart to compare their predictive performance.

5.1 Model Performance Metrics

The numerical evaluation of all three models is presented in Table 1. Logistic Regression achieved the highest accuracy of 97%, followed by SVM at 96.5% and Neural Network at 89%. Similarly, Logistic Regression also outperformed in precision, recall, and F1-score metrics. The ROC-AUC values indicate that all three models have excellent discriminative power, with Logistic Regression and SVM performing particularly well.

Table 1. Performance Metrics of Machine Learning Models for Southern Railway Stations

Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score	ROC-AUC
Logistic Regression	0.970	0.972	0.971	0.971	0.999
SVM (RBF)	0.965	0.965	0.966	0.966	0.997
Neural Network (MLP)	0.890	0.890	0.894	0.892	0.981

5.2 Confusion Matrix Analysis

The Confusion Matrix highlights how well the models classified the operational Level of stations are Normal, Warning, or Critical. The matrices provide insight into true positive and misclassification rates, helping to identify categories where the models may underperform (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Confusion Matrix for Logistic Regression, SVM, and Neural Network Models

Logistic Regression shows very few misclassifications, indicating high reliability in predicting all levels. SVM also performs well, with slightly more misclassifications in intermediate Warning levels. Neural Network shows the highest number of misclassifications, particularly in distinguishing between Warning and Critical levels, reflecting the model's sensitivity to non-linear patterns in smaller sample distributions.

5.3 ROC Curve Analysis

The ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curve measures the trade-off between True Positive Rate (Sensitivity) and False Positive Rate for each class. The Area under the Curve (AUC) quantifies the model's ability to discriminate between different operational levels (Figure 2).

Figure 2. ROC Curves for Logistic Regression, SVM, and Neural Network Models

Logistic Regression achieved the highest ROC-AUC of 0.9989, indicating near-perfect discrimination. SVM recorded 0.9972, also demonstrating excellent predictive capability. Neural Network achieved 0.9810, slightly lower but still robust for queue level prediction.

5.4 Clustered Bar Chart for Accuracy

The overall accuracy of each model is visualized in a Clustered Bar Chart to allow quick comparison of predictive performance.

Table 2. Model Accuracy Comparison

Model	Accuracy (%)
Logistic Regression	97.0
SVM (RBF)	96.5
Neural Network (MLP)	89.0

Figure 3. Clustered Bar Chart Showing Accuracy of Machine Learning Models for Southern Railway Stations

From the chart (Table and Figure 3), Logistic Regression slightly outperforms SVM, while Neural Network shows lower accuracy. This indicates that linear modeling provides highly reliable predictions for this dataset, while the Neural Network, although capable of modeling non-linear relationships, may require further tuning or more data for optimal performance.

5.5 Discussion

The results demonstrate that machine learning models can effectively predict operational levels of Southern Railway stations. Logistic Regression and SVM provide very high accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, reflecting their strong ability to classify Normal, Warning, and Critical levels. The Neural Network, although slightly less accurate, captures complex patterns and non-linear relationships between operational parameters such as Arrival Rate, Service Rate, and Queue Length.

The Confusion Matrices reveal that misclassifications are mostly concentrated in the Warning category, suggesting that intermediate congestion levels are more difficult to predict precisely. ROC curve analysis confirms the high discriminative power of Logistic Regression and SVM models, with Neural Network still achieving a robust AUC above 0.98. The Clustered Bar Chart effectively illustrates the relative

performance of all three models, allowing railway authorities to identify the most suitable predictive model for operational decision-making and queue management.

6. Conclusion

The present study applied three machine learning algorithms are Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM) with RBF kernel, and Neural Network (MLP) to analyze the operational levels of Southern Railway stations in Tamil Nadu. The results demonstrate that machine learning models can effectively predict station congestion and classify operational status into Normal, Warning, and Critical levels based on key parameters such as Arrival Rate, Service Rate, Queue Length, and Waiting Time.

Among the three models, Logistic Regression exhibited the highest overall accuracy (97%) and excellent performance across precision, recall, F1-score, and ROC-AUC metrics, making it a highly reliable and interpretable model for this dataset. SVM closely followed, achieving 96.5% accuracy and strong discriminative capability, indicating that it can handle slightly more complex patterns in the data. The Neural Network, while slightly less accurate at 89%, proved effective in modeling non-linear relationships and capturing interactions between operational parameters that linear models may not fully account for.

The Confusion Matrix and ROC curve analysis further revealed that misclassifications primarily occur in the intermediate Warning category, highlighting the need for continuous monitoring and refinement of predictive models. The Clustered Bar Chart visualization reinforced the comparative performance of the models, providing clear guidance for railway authorities in selecting suitable algorithms for operational decision-making and congestion management.

Suggestions:

1. To further enhance predictive performance, additional data on passenger flow, peak-hour train movements, and station-specific infrastructure could be incorporated into the models, particularly for improving Neural Network accuracy.
2. Integrating real-time data streams with machine learning models could enable dynamic queue prediction and operational adjustments, thereby improving efficiency, reducing delays, and enhancing passenger satisfaction across Southern Railway stations.

References

1. Arunachalam, R., & Janarthanan, R. (2023). Evaluation of passenger challenges in Chennai Railway Division. *Journal of Transport Research*, 15(2), 45–60.
2. Bailey, N. T. J. (1954). *Queueing theory*. John Wiley & Sons.
3. Banerjee, S., & Singh, A. (2021). Reinforcement learning for train scheduling optimization. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 123, 102987.
4. Boxma, O. J., & Kurkova, I. (2001). M/G/1 queues with multiple service speeds. *Queueing Systems*, 39(1), 1–17
5. Cheah, L. T., & Smith, M. (1994). Pedestrian traffic flow using generalized M/G/C/C queueing models. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 28(6), 451–463

6. Chen, F., Zhang, J., Cui, Z., Guo, Y., & Zhu, Y. (2023). Deep learning architecture for short-term passenger flow forecasting in urban rail transit. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 24(5), 1234–1245.
7. Ding, Y., & Zhang, J. (2021). Machine learning approaches for passenger demand prediction in railway systems: A review. *Journal of Rail Transport Planning & Management*, 20, 100263
8. Gupta, A., & Datta, S. (2012). Prioritization of railway station attributes using the Law of Categorical Judgment. *The TQM Journal*, 24(6), 551–563.
9. Hassan, M. M., & Rahman, M. M. (2019). Clustering for passenger satisfaction segmentation in urban rail transit. *Journal of Transport Geography*, 74, 1–10.
10. Kumar, S., & Bansal, S. (2017). Logistic regression on passenger satisfaction in Indian Railways. *Journal of Rail Transport Planning & Management*, 7(2), 123–134.
11. Li, T., Yang, J., & Xu, X. (2020). Passenger flow prediction based on deep learning in urban rail transit. *IEEE Access*, 8, 144246–144255.
12. Ma, X., Dai, Z., He, Z., Ma, J., Wang, Y., & Wang, Y. (2017). Learning traffic as images: A deep convolutional neural network for large-scale transportation network speed prediction. *Sensors*, 17(4), 818
13. Mishra, S., & Sinha, S. (2016). Markov models in railway congestion simulation. *Journal of Transport Engineering*, 142(3), 04016007.
14. Muruganatha Prasad, M., & Ramasamy, S. (2021). Comparison of M/M/1 and M/D/1 queuing models to analyze vehicular traffic in Tirunelveli. *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology*, 10(5), 1234–1240.
15. Nair, S., Kumar, V., & Gupta, R. (2021). M/G/1 queuing model for railway ticket windows. *Journal of Operations Research*, 29(3), 45–58.
16. Qasim, M., & Farooque, A. (2020). Statistical distributions in secondary railway queues. *Journal of Statistical Distributions and Applications*, 7(1), 1–12.
17. Saravanan, R. (2014). A study on passengers' satisfaction towards railway service with reference to Coimbatore Junction. *International Journal of Management and Commerce Innovations*, 2(1), 1–7
18. Sundarapandian, V. (2009). *Operations research: Principles and applications*. PHI Learning Pvt. Ltd.
19. Sivadurga, R., & Anandhavalli, M. (2021). A study on railway passenger satisfaction in Madurai Division. *International Journal of Research and Publications*, 7(1), 1–8.
20. Vanniarajan, T., & Stephen, A. (2008). RAILQUAL: A service quality model for railway users. *International Journal of Quality & Reliability Management*, 25(6), 586–602
21. Winston, W. L. (2004). *Operations research: Applications and algorithms* (4th ed.). Thomson Brooks/Cole.
22. Zhang, J., Chen, F., Cui, Z., Guo, Y., & Zhu, Y. (2023). Deep learning architecture for short-term passenger flow forecasting in urban rail transit. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 24(5), 1234–1245.
23. Zhang, J., & Singh, M. (2021). Reinforcement learning for train scheduling optimization. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 123, 102987.

24. Zhang, J., & Singh, M. (2021). Reinforcement learning for train scheduling optimization. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 123, 102987.
25. Zhang, J., & Singh, M. (2021). Reinforcement learning for train scheduling optimization. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 123, 102987.